

THE HAWAI‘I SUPERSITE: IMPROVED UNDERSTANDING OF HAWAIIAN VOLCANISM MADE POSSIBLE BY INCREASED DATA ACCESSIBILITY

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ABSTRACT

The Hawai‘i Supersite was established in 2008 to encourage basic research into Hawaiian volcanoes and their attendant hazards by making a diverse suite of ground-based, airborne, and satellite data available at no cost to the scientific community. These data include almost 10 TB of synthetic aperture radar imagery, which, in combination with other geological, geochemical, and geophysical measurements, have yielded insights into eruption dynamics, lava flow emplacement, surface deformation, and other processes. The major challenge facing the Supersite is the management, archiving, and distribution of the large volume of available data—a problem that only increases with time given the growing number of ground-based instruments and satellite missions, in particular. Provided that these challenges can be met, multidisciplinary scientific collaborations made possible by the Hawai‘i Supersite should continue to yield new insights into how Hawaiian and other volcanoes work, and the Supersite will serve as a model for how targeted research initiatives can impact the understanding of hazardous Earth processes.

Index Terms— Geodesy, Synthetic Aperture Radar, Volcanoes, Radar Interferometry, Hazards

1. INTRODUCTION

The Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories initiative, organized by the Group on Earth Observations, facilitates access to space-based, airborne, and ground-based data for regional areas exposed to geological threats. The principal objective is to encourage basic research of hazardous geological processes as a means of reducing the loss of life from geological disasters through improved access to multidisciplinary Earth science data.

As the location of two of the most active volcanoes in the world—Kīlauea and Mauna Loa—and one of the most seismically active places in the United States [1], Hawai‘i is an ideal volcano Supersite. Hawai‘i also has population and infrastructure exposed to volcanic and seismic hazards, a high likelihood of future eruptive activity and changes in existing activity, and a long history as a location that stimulates basic volcanological research thanks to over a

century of continuous multidisciplinary study. Kīlauea Volcano has been in a state of near-continuous eruption from a vent on its east rift zone since 1983 and from a vent within its summit caldera since 2008. Mauna Loa, which was most recently active in 1984 but experienced an episode of inflation during 2002–2009, is the largest active volcano by volume in the world, and its eruptions threaten populated areas.

The Hawai‘i Supersite was established in 2008 and made permanent in 2012. Over the course of its existence, SAR data have been provided to the Supersite by the Canadian, Japanese, European, Italian, and German space agencies. Well over 2000 individual SAR scenes are part of the Hawai‘i archive, amounting to nearly 10 TB of raw data. A diversity of ground-based data, including geodetic, seismic, and geochemical, are supplied by the U.S. Geological Survey’s Hawaiian Volcano Observatory and collaborators as part of Supersite implementation. The availability through the Supersite of such a broad suite of remote and terrestrial data has facilitated numerous new explorations into Hawaiian volcanism.

2. EXAMPLES OF SUPERSITE-AIDED RESEARCH INTO HAWAIIAN VOLCANISM

A large number of investigators regularly make use of both remotely sensed and ground-based data provided through the Hawai‘i Supersite. Their research has resulted in many new studies concerning how Hawaiian volcanoes work, several of which are highlighted below.

2.1. March 5–9, 2011, fissure eruption and lava lake drainage

On March 5, 2011, the lava lake at Kīlauea’s summit began to drain as a new dike intruded the volcano’s east rift zone and initiated the 4.5-day-long Kamoamoā fissure eruption. Seven SAR images from different satellites were acquired during or immediately following the eruption (Figure 1). Modeling of dike opening using these data, combined with ground-based GPS, tilt, and crack measurements, indicated that the dike fluctuated in volume over the course of the eruption and even expanded following the end of the eruptive activity (which was confirmed by post-eruption

Figure 1. Examples of interferograms spanning Kīlauea’s March 5–9, 2011, Kamoamoia fissure eruption. The deformation indicates intrusion of a dike into the volcano’s east rift zone [2]. Interferograms are depicted with a 10 cm color cycle. In each panel, gray/black arrows indicate the satellite heading and look directions, respectively, and the approximate incidence angle, from vertical, in the center of the image. Satellite and image ending date are shown in the upper right corner.

Figure 2. Average line-of-sight velocities (left) and time series (right) for TerraSAR-X descending orbital path 24 during 2008–2012. Numbers on each velocity map indicate the locations of pixels in the corresponding time series. Black lines in the time series give vent area over time, and red vertical bars mark small explosions from the summit vent [4]. Grey bars above the x axis mark time periods of similar vent-rim deformation style, with rapid subsidence (periods 1 and 3) alternating with less rapid subsidence (periods 2 and 4).

UAVSAR airborne data) [2]. These results—the first time multiple independent interferograms have been used to track the temporal evolution of a single eruptive event—would not have been possible without the diversity of data available to the Hawai‘i Supersite. In addition, SAR data acquired through the Supersite were combined with gravity measurements spanning drainage of Kīlauea’s summit lava lake. These results indicated that the density of the upper ~150 meters of the lava lake was about 1000 kg/m³—similar to that of water [3].

2.2. Deformation around Kīlauea’s summit eruptive vent

SAR data from X-band satellites, like COSMO-SkyMed and TerraSAR-X, have the advantage of not only frequent acquisitions, but also excellent spatial resolution. As a result,

interferograms can track centimeter-scale deformation over short time scales. For example, TerraSAR-X interferograms indicate subsidence that is variable in time and space within a few hundred meters of the rim of Kīlauea’s summit eruptive vent (Figure 2). The subsidence rate appears to provide an indication of the stability of the vent rim [4]—especially important because rock falls into the lava lake within the vent can generate small, locally hazardous explosions. Ground-based monitoring of the vent rim is not possible, confirming the value of InSAR measurements for tracking this activity.

2.3. Lava flow mapping

Mapping the locations and advance rates of lava flows is of critical importance in assessing hazards due to emplacement

Figure 3. The extent of lava flows from Kīlauea's east rift zone eruption during November 25, 2007–March 12, 2008, based on InSAR coherence [6]. Using these data, flow advance rates can be calculated (inset), which compare well with ground-based estimates and provide important input to assessment of lava flow hazards.

of flows [1]. The Hawaiian Volcano Observatory typically conducts surveys of lava activity through aerial reconnaissance, satellite observation of thermal anomalies, and ground-based camera imagery. Unfortunately, aerial surveys are expensive, and satellite and camera imagery may be obscured by weather. Coherence mapping from InSAR overcomes these issues—the Hawai'i Supersite has thousands of freely accessible SAR data, and those images are not impacted by cloud cover. Because changes in the scattering properties of the ground result in a loss of coherence between the times of SAR acquisitions, coherence loss can be used to map active lava flows [5]. Coherence does not vary according to look angle, so data from different satellites and orbital paths can be combined to map lava flow activity with excellent temporal resolution (Figure 3)—perhaps only a few days between data takes, which is a much higher rate than is available from other space- or ground-based data [6].

3. FUTURE DIRECTIONS FOR THE HAWAII'I SUPERSITE

The Hawai'i Supersite has very successfully enabled scientists from around the world to conduct collaborative research relating to Hawai'i's recent volcanic and seismic

activity. Currently, the greatest challenge facing the Supersite is managing the large archive of SAR, airborne, and ground-based data and making those data available to interested researchers. This problem will grow with time as new satellite missions are launched—for instance, JAXA's ALOS-2 and ESA's Sentinel-1 missions—so new resources will need to be allocated for data management, archiving, and distribution. Nevertheless, the results of scientific studies made using Hawai'i Supersite data thus far have shown the enormous benefits of access to multidisciplinary data from Hawaiian volcanoes, and the effort should therefore continue into the future. Ultimately, it is hoped that the Hawai'i Supersite will facilitate large-scale collaborations on complex problems of extreme importance to society, for instance, volcanic flank instability, magma plumbing system structure, and eruption precursors.

4. REFERENCES

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